

An Analysis Effect of Service Quality and Location on Consumer Satisfaction at Taman Asoka Asri Medan

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Abstract— Consumer satisfaction has an important role in a company for the sustainability of the company. This is the main reason for a company to raise customer satisfaction, so it can support the company's plans for further expansion. To measure consumer satisfaction in housing can be seen from the quality of service (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangible) and locations that consumers receive. The purpose of this study is to find out and analyze the influence of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, tangible, and location on customer satisfaction. The populations in this study were consumers who bought and occupied house at Taman Asoka Asri. Total sample in this study are 69 samples. In this study researcher used survey methods for data collection and used multiple linear regression analysis tools. From the results of the study, it was found that the quality of service which includes (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangible), and the location together have a significant effect on consumer satisfaction housing Taman Asoka Asri Medan. For each independent variable: reliability has a positive and significant effect; responsiveness has a positive and significant effect; assurance have a positive and insignificant effect; empathy has a positive and insignificant effect; tangible has a positive and significant effect; location has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction at Taman Asoka Asri Medan.

Keywords— Service Quality, Location and Consumer Satisfaction, Multiple linear regression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Property company is a company that is directly or indirectly related to the interests of the community in terms of construction of apartments, condominiums, housing (Real Estate), offices, and more. Community property products especially need a place to stay in order to meet their basic needs. Competition in the business world property encourages entrepreneurs to come up with new thoughts can build products and services that provide more value to consumers. In the world of real estate consumer satisfaction in the very influential in the achievement of the vision of the company. In achievement, the consumer was supposed to have or feel satisfaction on products they get or have. Satisfaction of consumers have an important role in a company or organization for the sustainability of the company. This has been the main reason for a company to increase consumer satisfaction already. The company is the main consideration in improving consumer satisfaction is due to the more intense climate of competition in the field of residential development in the city of Medan, thus increasing the satisfaction of

consumers can support the corporate plan in the next expansion.

Despite having no problems in property sales at Taman Asoka Asri business property development is on the rise and competitors who continue to grow by offering quality service, and a convenient location to the consumer. Company parties admit this quite become a nuisance and a threat to the company by seeing a growing trend at the moment many consumers who make the home as one investment vehicle than to be assigned to the family. Sold all the houses that exhaustion of the company have not quite made the company feel happy and secure because there is no consumer satisfaction, performance and corporate image of the company may be declining slowly. In a survey, the researchers did a short interview with 20 people consumer related service quality, and location. Based on the results obtained some consumer responses can affect customer satisfaction, namely:

1. Most of the residents interviewed in the survey said that in those less satisfied over the existing service and provided by the company.
2. The absence of a list of complaints provided by the company even though the company's Party has already done in another way by making group chat to respond to the complaint but it was judged less effective by consumers. Residents want the complaint form and input as a form of appreciation and critique the occupants against the management in managing the housing.
3. Some facilities are not realized, it is inversely proportional when first-party companies market products which in this case is home to consumers by stating that there is a sports facility in the housing.
4. The existence of concerns some consumers over the area of access to housing. The concerns of the consumer is a lot of vehicles are mengebut and can be a threat to consumers who want to exit sign in the housing.

II. RELATED WORK

Bayu [1] indicates that the quality of product and service quality has a positive influence and significantly to consumer satisfaction. The influence of the quality of the product towards the satisfaction of 0.548, while the influence of the quality of service towards satisfaction of 0.381.

Dwi [2] indicates that the quality of the service and the marketing mix consists of product, price, and location of the influential positively and significantly to consumer

satisfaction on a housing Residence Stella Setia Budi Medan. Based on test results in partial variable quality of service is the dominant factor in influencing consumer satisfaction.

Jeanne et al. [3] shows the five dimensions of service quality on the consumer's apartment in the city of Surabaya which consists of reliability, responsiveness, empathy, performance, and physical evidences proved to significantly shape the variable service quality, where this is indicated by the value of the critical ratio of each of these factors or dimensions greater than 2.

Grace et al. [4] promotional mix shows a positive and significant effect against the purchasing decisions and consumer satisfaction. The negative effect of price perceptions towards purchasing decisions and consumer satisfaction. Location of positive and significant effect of purchases and negatively to customer satisfaction. The management should pay attention to and improve the mix of corporate campaign against purchasing decisions to maintain customer satisfaction.

Rudika et al. [5] shows those factors had a positive and significant influence. Factors that influence most facilities large followed by residential location factors.

Timotici et al. [6] indicates that the residents felt satisfied against the overall condition of their housing. But the results of the Anova analysis showed that there is a difference of satisfaction on a number of factors, namely the infrastructure factors and means. While the results of the analysis of factors suggests that factors the quality of buildings, the design and the price is a major factor in consideration of satisfaction assessment by residents.

Riski [7] indicates that the price and the location of significant effect against complacency. The price and the location does not have significant influence towards Word of Mouth directly. The price and location have significant influence towards word of mouth through satisfaction as intervening. Quality of service the positive and significant effect against the satisfaction and towards Word of Mouth national housing resident IV. Variables that have the greatest influence Satisfaction directly against is the quality of service. Variables that have the greatest influence towards word of mouth directly is satisfaction.

Risnawati [8] stated product quality signifi influential right towards customer satisfaction. Quality of service effect significantly to consumer satisfaction. Product quality and service quality of influential signifi right towards customer satisfaction.

Fachrul [9] shows that simultaneously variable pricing, design, and location of the influential buying decision significantly to housing in Banda Aceh. It is characterized by the value $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($68.938 > 2.690$) at the level of significance of 0.000. prove that the simultaneous price, design, and location of the influential buying decision significantly to housing in Banda Aceh.

Putu [10] property attributes that have significant influence towards customer satisfaction. Building quality attributes and prices is the dominant attribute with the influence towards customer satisfaction.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research according to the level of explanation is the quantitative and descriptive with regard to the nature of this research is a descriptive explanatory. This research was conducted on a Taman Asoka Asri Housing while time studies are conducted from May – July 2018.

Methods of Data analysis used is :

1. Descriptive Analysis Method
2. Inferensial Statistical Analysis Methods
3. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Of Data

Multiple linear regression analysis models that consist of structural equations are formulated with the following equation :

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + e$$

Description:

Y = Consumer Satisfaction

P = The Regression Coefficient

X1 = Reliability

X2 = Responsiveness

X3 = Assurance

X4 = Emphaty

X5 = Physical evidence

X6 = Location

e = Term of Error

Determination of the sample by using the following calculation solving:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

n = the number of samples

N = number of Population

e = fault tolerance limits

Then the obtained sample size as follows:

$$n = \frac{218}{1 + 218(0.1^2)} = 68.55 \approx 69 \text{ people}$$

A sample of these studies amounted to 68.55 rounded into 69 people. The data required in the writing of this collected from February until July 2018, both primary as well as secondary data is data. Methods undertaken to collect primary data is charging a number of rounds of questions in the questionnaire by respondents. Whereas, secondary data obtained through the study of librarianship.

Technique of filling questionnaire is one way of collecting primary data by using the checklist questions against objects that are examined. Dissemination of the questionnaire was conducted to identify the influence of dimensions of service quality, and location against consumer satisfaction, consumer satisfaction and influence in shaping consumer loyalty against PT. Arians Land.

Measurement of questions in the questionnaire using Likert scale so that it can show the extent of the interest of any latent variables and observed. Likert scales used has a value of 1 to 5 with 1 description as taraf strongly disagree, 2 disagree, as level 3 as degrees of somewhat less agree, score 4 as levels agree, score 5 as adequate strongly agree.

The variables in this study are as follows:

1. *Independent Variable*

Variable independent that affect or be a cause of the onset or changing a variable is bound (the dependent). In this research which is the free variable is the quality of reliability (X 1), Responsiveness (X 2), Assurance (X 3), empathy (X 4), Physical evidence (X 5), and location (X 6).

2. *Dependen Variable*

The dependent variable is affected or which become due as a result of the free variable (independent). In this research which is the variable terikatnya is the customer satisfaction (Y).

IV. DISCUSSION

This research aims to know the: (1) influence of reliability against consumer satisfaction, (2) the influence of responsiveness towards consumer satisfaction, (3) the influence of assurance against consumer satisfaction, (4) influence of empathy toward customer satisfaction, (5) the influence of physical evidence against consumer satisfaction, (6) the influence of the location of the consumer, and (7) the influence of reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, empathy, physical evidence and locations together in Taman Asoka Asri. The analysis used in the study include descriptive analysis, regression analysis, and hypothesis testing. Based on the regression equation obtained analysis results that can be explained that the direction of the keofisien regression independent variable consisting of X1 (reliability), X2 (Responsiveness), X3 (Assurance), X4 (Empathy), X5 (physical evidence), X6 (location) is positive or a positive effect towards consumer satisfaction in Taman Asoka Asri Housing. This is supported by the value of the correlation coefficient R is obtained, if the ditabulasikan into multiple correlation coefficient on the interpretation interval coefficient that is located at the level of a strong relationship. This means that the relationship of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, physical evidence and locations against consumer satisfaction is at the level of a strong relationship.

It can also be explained from the value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) obtained with the value of the coefficient of determination (R Square) of 0.569. This means that 56.9% consumer satisfaction is affected by the variable reliability,

responsiveness, assurance, empathy, physical evidence and locations on this research, while the rest was 43.1% influenced by variables other than the independent variable used in This research.

Based Table I, multiple linear regression equation is obtained as follows.

$$Y = -0,037 + 0,237X_1 + 0,252X_2 + 0,007X_3 + 0,103X_4 + 0,219X_5 + 0,244X_6 + e$$

Based on the results in table I, unknown:

- The value of the coefficient of reliability is 0.237, i.e. is positive. This means a positively influential reliability towards customer satisfaction. Note the value t count 2.380 > 1.99 table t and Sig 0.020 < 0.05, then < influential reliability significantly to consumer satisfaction.
- The value of the coefficient of responsiveness was 0.252, i.e. is positive. This means a positively influential responsiveness towards customer satisfaction. Note the value t count 2.110 > 1.99 table t and Sig 0.039 < 0.05, then influential responsiveness significantly to consumer satisfaction.
- The value of the coefficient of collateral is 0.007, i.e. is positive. This means a positively influential guarantee against consumer satisfaction. Note the value t count 0.060 < 1.99 table t and Sig 0.952 > 0.05, then the guarantee do not affect significantly to consumer satisfaction.
- The value of the coefficient of empathy is 0.103, i.e. is positive. This means a positively influential empathy toward customer satisfaction. Note the value t count 1.041 < 1.99 table t and Sig 0.302 > 0.05, then empathy won't effect significantly to consumer satisfaction.
- The value of the coefficient of the physical evidence is 0.219, i.e. is positive. This means a positively influential physical evidence against consumer satisfaction. Note the value t count 2.027 > 1.99 table t and Sig 0.047 < 0.05, then < physical evidence effect significantly to consumer satisfaction.
- The value of the coefficient is 0.244, i.e. is positive. This means a positively influential location towards the satisfaction of the consumer. Note the value t calculate 2.129 > 1.99 table t and Sig 0.037 < 0.05, then the location of the influential significantly to consumer satisfaction.

TABLE I. Power consumption details for one different geographical area

Model		Coefficients ^a					Collinearity Statistics	
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	-.037	.369		-.099	.921		
	Reliability (X1)	.237	.100	.243	2.380	.020	.669	1.496
	Responsiveness (X2)	.252	.119	.231	2.110	.039	.581	1.722
	Assurance (X3)	.007	.110	.006	.060	.952	.638	1.567
	Empathy (X4)	.103	.098	.102	1.041	.302	.722	1.386
	Physical evidence (X5)	.219	.108	.215	2.027	.047	.618	1.619
	Location (X6)	.244	.114	.232	2.129	.037	.587	1.703

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Satisfaction (Y)

V. CONCLUSION

Based on data obtained from the results of the analysis, some conclusions can be drawn then as follows: This research aims to examine and analyze the influence of the quality of service and location against consumer satisfaction in Taman Asoka Asri Housing, Medan, North Sumatera. The quality of the services that include (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and physical evidence), and locations together influential significantly to consumer satisfaction in Taman Asoka Asri Housing Medan. For each dependent variable: reliability and significant positive effect; the positive responsiveness of influential and significant; collateral effect positive and insignificant; the positive effect of empathy and insignificant; physical evidence of positive and significant effect; location of influential positive and significantly to consumer satisfaction in Taman Asoka Asri Housing Medan.

Advice that can be given are as follows:

1. To improve reliability and responsiveness is conducting a variety of training human resources competency development focus towards services in the field of property against the staff of the service.
2. To increase the guarantee was necessary increased the number of security personnel that maintain and install CCTV at every junction blocks in Taman Asoka Asri Housing.
3. To increase empathy is making family gathering consumer with the management that aims for mutual sharing between parties management with consumers.
4. To increase the physical evidence is doing the renovation of the office building, then realizing the facilities already promised in the beginning such as swimming pools, sports grounds, and means that can be used by residents to relax and play for kids.
5. To improve the site is adding a new task for the security at the front post to help process incoming and outgoing flow of occupants to Highway from housing.
6. For the next researcher, in this study, the variables examined are reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, physical evidence, and location. These variables can be used as initial data for further research in

developing similar studies so that it gets a wider knowledge about the increased consumer satisfaction. It is hoped the presence of further research conducted by digging another variable not yet identified in this research.

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